

Uterine Rupture in Unscarred Bicornuate Uterus-A Post Sterilization Failure

Aarathi K Jayraj¹, Nanthini Saravanan^{2*}

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research (JIPMER), Karaikal, Puducherry

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research (JIPMER), Karaikal, Puducherry

Citation: Aarathi K Jayraj, Nanthini Saravanan. Uterine Rupture in Unscarred Bicornuate Uterus-A Post Sterilization Failure. *Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(14):1-3.

Received Date: 22 August, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 24 August, 2023; **Published Date:** 26 August, 2023

***Corresponding author:** Nanthini Saravanan, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research (JIPMER), Karaikal, Puducherry, India

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CLINICAL IMAGE

Uterine rupture in bicornuate uterus post sterilization failure

Figure 1. Bicornuate uterus

Rent in the
right horn

Figure 2. Rent in the upper segment of right horn (Blue arrow)

Figure 3. Rent repaired in two layers & presence of left horn prevented bladder extension during uterine rupture

Tubectomy on left tube

No evidence of
tubectomy on right tube

Figure 4. Left (A) and right (B) fallopian tube attached to left and right horn respectively.

A 28 years old gravida 3 para 2 live 2 post sterilisation was referred to district headquarters at term in view of previous 1 caesarean section on May 2022 in early labor. Maternal tachycardia was seen along with recurrent variable deceleration in cardiotocography. With doubtful scar integrity, she was posted for emergency laparotomy. Intraoperatively, fetus and placenta were seen in the peritoneal cavity. Patient had undiagnosed bicornuate uterus. 10 cm rent was seen in the upper segment of unscarred right horn which was repaired in two layers with 1-0 vicryl. Bladder was not involved which was further confirmed with methylene blue. Presence of left horn prevented bladder extension during uterine rupture. Evidence of tubectomy was seen in left fallopian tube. No evidence of tubectomy on right fallopian tube attached to right horn. Patient had one cervix and one vagina.

In cases of sterilization failure, it is important to look for congenital uterine anomaly.